

Characterisation of a Customised Diffraction Grating

A thesis submitted
in partial fulfillment for the award of the degree of

Master of Technology

in

Optical Engineering

by

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Certificate

This is to certify that the thesis titled *Characterisation of a Customised Diffraction Grating* submitted by **Shaun Ethan Chaudhury Phangcho**, to the Indian Institute of Space Science and Technology, Thiruvananthapuram, in partial fulfillment for the award of the degree of **Master of Technology in Optical Engineering** is a bona fide record of the original work carried out by him/her under my supervision. The contents of this thesis, in full or in parts, have not been submitted to any other Institute or University for the award of any degree or diploma.

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I declare that this thesis titled *Characterisation of a Customised Diffraction Grating* submitted in partial fulfillment for the award of the degree of **Master of Technology in Optical Engineering** is a record of the original work carried out by me under the supervision of **Shri Krishnamurthy T(PDSTL, Ex-LEOS), Dr Manvendra Singh (IRDE-DRDO), Shri Abhijit Chakraborty (IRDE-DRDO), Dr Dinesh N Naik(IIST)** and has not formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, associateship, fellowship, or other titles in this or any other Institution or University of higher learning. In keeping with the ethical practice in reporting scientific information, due acknowledgments have been made wherever the findings of others have been cited.

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Abstract

The requirement of the project for designing and building a characterisation instrument stemmed from development of a hyperspectral imager in the Short Wave Infrared (SWIR) region. In such a scenario, selection of a dispersive element is crucial to the system performance. Various dispersive elements such as diffraction gratings, prisms and Linear Variable Filters (LVF) exist and are briefly mentioned in this project. Each has their own advantages and disadvantages. A diffraction grating was chosen due to its virtues and manageable vices. A study of the various types of diffraction gratings is also carried out to better understand the parameters such as relative efficiency, order intensity ratio, blaze angle, etc. Such parameters after fabrication are required to be measured, calibrated and tested before assembling in the actual payload. For the explicit purpose of measuring said quantities, design of a Grating Characterisation Monochromator (GCM) has been proposed, manufactured and tested alongside necessary opto-mechanical and electrical components. The Monochromator is a highly complex and ingenious apparatus built. Its operation is a sophisticated process that requires accurate calibration beforehand. The optical design is carried in Zemax OpticStudio 22 and 23. The entire end-to-end optical design and simulation procedure is explained in detail. The design iterations that the author came across while carrying out the design is also shown and the comparative study review taken place is also included. It is made sure that a theoretical analysis is first done and then finally the experimental results are evaluated. It is known and acknowledged that optical alignment is a highly sensitive and difficult process and hence final assembly of the optical elements is carried out using state-of-the-art optical metrology tools like *ZygoTM* Dynafiz interferometer and Leica Theodolite. The accurate calibration is performed multiple times to ensure repeatability is maintained. As the experimental results surface, further analysis in MATLAB provides a clearer picture of the importance of building the Grating Characterisation Monochromator as principal part of this thesis.

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Abbreviations

SWIR - Short Wavelength Infrared

VNIR - Visible Near Infrared

μm - Micrometer

nm - Nanometer

GCM - Grating Characterisation Monochromator

LDE - Lens Data Editor

MCE - Multi-Configuration Editor

EEFL - Effective Focal Length

WFNO - Working F Number

TOTR - Total Optical Track Length

Nomenclature

n - Diffraction Order

λ - Wavelength

d - Groove spacing

θ - Blaze angle

ϕ - Angle of rotation of grating

α - Angle of incidence

β - Angle of diffraction

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Brief Overview of Hyperspectral Imagers

One definition for imaging spectrometry is “the acquisition of images in several contiguous, registered, spectral bands such that for each pixel of the sensor, a radiance spectrum can be derived. Imaging spectrometry resulted in different technologies with advancements in optics, computer algorithms for data processing, electronics and other fields.

Before the emergence of Hyperspectral Imagers, there were Panchromatic and Multispectral imaging payloads. Panchromatic imagers are able to capture information in the visible and near Infrared bands; whereas Multispectral imagers are able to capture information in the visible, near Infrared and Short Wave Infrared. A panchromatic image uses a single band that combines Red, Green, and Blue bands, allowing for a greater spatial resolution. The resulting image does not contain any wavelength-specific information. When it comes to detecting brightness differences, a panchromatic imager is better in comparison to its multispectral counterpart. This is due to the smaller amounts of light energy available for multispectral bands compared to the Red, Green, and Blue bands. In order to compensate for the lack of brightness, multispectral detectors are required to sample larger areas – which translates into larger pixels and, subsequently, smaller spatial resolution in an image. A multispectral image is a collection of the same scene at discrete wavelengths to form an image stack containing spatial, spectral and radiometric information.

Hyperspectral Imagers are able to deliver finer spatial and spectral resolution alongside radiometric resolution. The information captured is stacked and can be viewed for analysis in Geographic Information System (GIS) softwares such as QGIS, ArcGIS, ENVI, ERDAS Imagine. The generated information is stored in the form of a cube called a hyperspectral

data cube which contains spatial, spectral and radiometric information simultaneously.

1.2 Scope of Work

The scope of this project is multi-fold and so is divided across various sections and chapters throughout. The primary objective is to create a characterisation setup for a multiple-blazed customised diffraction grating that is specific to the SWIR Hyperspectral Imaging Payload. A brief summary is provided point-wise.

- To characterise a multi-blazed dispersive diffraction grating used in a Short Wavelength Infrared (SWIR) Hyperspectral Imaging Payload.
- To understand the payload specific requirements.
- To run MATLAB-based simulations for better understanding of blazed grating related calculations.
- To create an integrated optical system for characterisation of the payload grating.
- To check the possibility of performing absolute and relative diffraction efficiency calculations before system assembly and characterisation of the grating.
- To integrate the entire test setup along with optical, mechanical and electronic components.
- To calibrate the test setup for scanning the wavelength from 900-2500 nm of -1,+1,-2,+2 orders and their spectral characteristics such as Full Width Half Maxima (FWHM).
- To obtain relative efficiency and intensity ratio results, record the grating performance and compare to the theoretical requirements.
- To look for the feasibility for generalising this unique setup for other different diffraction grating characterisations.

1.3 Payload Details

The payload is a space-borne SWIR (Short Wavelength Infrared) Hyperspectral Imager working in the wavelength range of 900-2500 μm . Hyperspectral Imaging is evolving to

be a rapidly growing field in passive remote sensing. Due to it having high spatial and spectral resolution, its usage is wide and varied including scientific purposes. The detector used for the SWIR payload is an MCT detector (Mercury Cadmium Telluride) with an array size of 1000x256 pixels and a pixel pitch of 30 μm . There are 80 spectral bands formed each with a resolution or Full Width Half Maxima (FWHM) of 20 nm . There are 1000 pixels in the spatial direction and 256 in the spectral direction. The MCT detector is calibrated such that 16 pixels (8 pixels either side) are left for redundancy and alignment purposes. This then ensures that each band is taken care of and read by 3 detector pixels ($240/80 = 3$).

The optics uses a configuration of a Fore optics, Field Correcting Optics (FCO) and Offner. The fore optics consists of a Ritchey-Chretien (R-C) telescopic design. The rays then travel through the Field Correcting Lenses which correct for higher order aberrations such as astigmatism and field curvature for different fields. The Offner relay is a spectrometer configuration that provides spectral resolution in a compact mold. Figure 1.1 shows the rays traced in the final design configuration provided by Paras Defense and Space Technologies Limited (PDSTL) and Instruments Research and Development Establishment (IRDE-DRDO)

Figure 1.1: Optical Configuration and Ray Trace of the SWIR Hyperspectral Imager
Source : Paras Defense and Space Technologies Limited (PDSTL), Instruments Research and Development Establishment (IRDE-DRDO)

1.4 Dispersive Elements

Hyperspectral Imagers stand out due to the contiguous band information that they generate. This is done optically by using a dispersion. A prism, diffraction grating and Linear Variable Filter (LVF) provide this option of a dispersive element.

A prism refracts light in a wavelength-dependent manner resulting in non-linear dispersion which requires an algorithm or image processing to correct for the non-linearity. However, prisms have a efficiency throughput of upto 90 percent. A prism doesn't have 2nd order interference of wavelengths.

A Linear Variable Filter (LVF) or wedge filter is a wavelength filter with different spectral bands arrayed into a single filter block. Its disadvantage is that its signal throughput isn't as high as a prism's and its resolution is coarse.

A diffraction grating overcomes the challenges that a prism and LVF would have. A grating has a linear dispersion and good signal throughput and efficiency. However, it does suffer from 2nd order interference. It also doesn't suffer from absorption effects the way prisms and LVFs do. Table 1.1 summarises the advantages and disadvantages of using a prism and grating.

Table 1.1: Dispersive Element Comparison

Type	Prism	Grating
Spectral Resolution	1-10nm variable	1-20nm constant
Wavelength Range	400-2500nm with multiple prisms	400-2500nm with single grating
Efficiency	Upto 90 percent constant	Max 70 percent at single blaze wavelength
Order interference	None	Yes, second overlaps first in excess of one octave

Chapter 2

Methodology

This chapter's first section details the literature review carried out in search of similar characterisation setups for measuring blazed gratings efficiency and their relative intensity ratios. The next section tells the grating specifications and base theory used.

2.1 Literature Survey

Offner-based [1] concentric spectrometers are used in Hyperspectral missions due to their compactness, simplicity and efficacy. Further changes were made by Chrisp [2] wherein he divided the singular concave mirror into two mirrors - primary and tertiary Mirror. This increased the degrees of freedom for an optical engineer to control aberrations. Planar gratings are usually used in monochromators; concave gratings in portable spectrometers. Li et al. [3] provides good insight into different grating technologies used. Convex gratings are used in high fidelity applications such as airborne and space borne scenarios. Further improvements have been made by Reimers J et al. [4] such as introducing freeform surfaces which also correct for distortions while maintaining the compactness of the instrument. These Offner-Chrisp spectrometers have had more recent developments wherein optics used are freeform surfaces and the grating is replaced by a freeform grating [5]. Convex gratings while seldom used can also function as master gratings for concave gratings. Master gratings are those gratings that are used for replicating similar gratings. Master gratings are expensive to make however they form a basis for further replication of said grating. Characterisation of gratings for diffraction efficiency and wavefront error consist of different kinds of setups. Wavefront testing can be done using a custom built Offner type null test. Li et al. explains the setup they used for wavefront testing thoroughly.

Apart from wavefront testing, the groove profile can be measured using atomic force mi-

crosscopy which is a form of direct measurement. The integrity of the grating can also be measured indirectly in two ways; one by using a Fizeau Interferometer such as Zygo Dynafiz and another is the Nulling Wavefront Metrology method. Conducting profile measurements are necessary when it comes to any optical elements and gratings are no different. Gratings can be reflective or transmissive and are prepared in various ways as well. Some of the ways include holographic fabrication [6], electron beam lithography [7], mechanical ruling engines and ultra precision diamond tools [8]. Varied Line Space Gratings [9] also have been studied which vary the groove spacing as the grooves are ruled. The variation is not periodic however is well defined. It has found use in spectroscopic systems such as synchrotron light sources.

Under ruled reflective gratings, various groove profiles have been created and studied. Correlations have been drawn between diffraction efficiency and groove depth of the grating. For convex gratings, the grooves are made in two ways : equal along the arc of radius of curvature of the element and equal along the projection (ie. perpendicular to the normal of the surface) of the grating. The groove shape can be rectangular which would typically have a low efficiency or they could be sawtooth shaped and therefore blazed which increases the efficiency of the grating.

A spectrometer characterisation setup that is required is a novel way to characterise the specific SWIR grating payload and is not found commonly in literature as such. Instead, individual spectrometers to characterise specific commercial gratings are available. A turnkey solution for a spectrometer to check for the entire SWIR spectrum and their orders is not available when this thesis was written. The associated challenges are therefore taken up as part of the project.

2.2 Customized Grating Details

The grating decided for use in the SWIR payload is a convex reflective diffraction grating. The novelty in the design lies in the usage of a convex grating instead of planar or concave gratings. Concave and planar gratings are easier to fabricate compared to convex ones. However, with the complexity of a convex grating come added advantages as well. A convex grating can broaden and improve spectral resolution while also acting as a master grating for other gratings. Aberration correction can also be done with a convex grating. A convex grating also provides a feasibility of making the entire system more compact.

The grating groove period is 32 grooves/*mm*. The number of grooves decides the required dispersion. It is multi-blazed. The grating is also made to perform such that the intensity distribution is more for the -1 order than the $+1$ order of any respective wavelength. This was decided due to the -1 order ray bundle was falling at more favourable position on the detector than the $+1$ order. The favourable position recommended is derived from the geometry of the Offner and stray light analysis.

The blaze wavelengths are decided via an atmospheric transmission profile generated in MODTRAN. MODTRAN is a program used to model electromagnetic radiation propagating through the atmosphere. Figure 2.1 gives us a good estimate of the wavelength specific transmittance of the Earth's atmosphere. The payload is designed to work in the SWIR region which starts from 900 *nm* and ends at 2500 *nm*. Hence, the transmission plot generated is in the same region as well. The relation between blaze wavelength selection and the plot is that the wavelengths which have a low transmittance (<0.4) are boosted by blazing the grating at those wavelengths.

The selected grating is fabricated with blaze wavelengths at 1130, 1470 and 1780 *nm*. The grooves for a convex grating can be fabricated in two ways: equal along the arc (or radius of curvature) of the grating surface or equal along the projection of the grating surface. The grating used for study and experimentation is convex grating whose grooves are along the arc of the surface. Equal along the arc fabrication type gives a better (lower) RMS Wavefront Error compared to equal along the projection. It is fabricated by using ultra precision machining method called Single Point Diamond Turning (SPDT).

Atmosphere Model ⓘ

Water Column (atm-cm) ⓘ

Ozone Column (atm-cm) ⓘ

CO₂ (ppmv) ⓘ

CO (ppmv) ⓘ

CH₄ (ppmv) ⓘ

Ground Temperature (K) ⓘ

Ground Albedo ⓘ

Aerosol Model ⓘ

Visibility (km) ⓘ

Sensor Altitude ⓘ

Sensor Zenith ⓘ

Spectral Units Wavenumbers (cm⁻¹) Microns (μm)

Spectral Range μm μm

Resolution μm

Figure 2.1: Wavelength vs Transmittance plot simulated in MODTRAN

Figure 2.2: Grating groove design types : Left - Equal along groove(arc) Right - Equal along projection

The blazed grating made is a zone-wise blazed grating wherein you have 1130 *nm* blazed at zone one, 1430 *nm* at zone 2 and then 1780 *nm* blazed at zone 3. A representation is shown below in Figure 2.3

Figure 2.3: Multi-Blazed Grating scheme for the grating used in this study

Chapter 3

Theoretical Basis

This chapter deals with the base theory of diffraction and diffraction gratings taken from the Diffraction Grating Handbook [10].

The diffraction equation is highlighted above in Equation 3.1 and the schematic diagram is shown in Figure 3.1

Figure 3.1: Single Slit Diffraction Scheme

$$n\lambda = d\sin\theta \quad (3.1)$$

Where,

n is the order number of the maxima.

λ is the wavelength.

d is the distance between slits.

θ is the diffraction angle

A diffraction grating can be considered to be a multiple slit diffraction. Figure 3.2 shows the geometry used while describing a reflective diffraction grating. Diffraction gratings perform a very important function in Hyperspectral Imaging systems. Gratings diffract the incident radiation into its constituent wavelengths such that the diffraction angle changes for each wavelength for a given angle of incidence. Thus, the diffracted wavelengths give the spectral information in the perpendicular direction to the slit orientation and spatial information along the slit orientation for different fields giving both spatial and spectral information on the focal plane array of the sensor.

Figure 3.2: Diffraction Grating Geometry.

Source : Oxford Instruments Andor

$$n\lambda = d(\sin\alpha + \sin\beta) \quad (3.2)$$

$$\theta = (\alpha + \beta)/2 \quad (3.3)$$

$$h = d\sin\theta \quad (3.4)$$

Where,

n is the diffracted order.

λ is the wavelength.

d is the groove spacing.

α is the incident angle on the grating.

β is the diffracted angle.

θ is the blaze wavelength.

h is the groove depth.

The Equations 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4 form the theoretical basis of this project. The grating specifications and angle calculation were done using them.

Scalar and Rigorous Diffraction Theory are two methods to calculate absolute and relative

Figure 3.3: Zoomed in view of a blazed grating and displaying associated nomenclature

diffraction efficiency. Scalar theory does not account for the polarisation state (Transverse Electric or Transverse Magnetic) of the incident radiation or light. This approximation is valid for diffraction gratings having a very low blaze angle (<5 degrees). Table 3.2 gives a clear view of the family of gratings based blaze angle.

Rigorous Vector Diffraction Theory account for the polarisation incident and the further distributed energies among the diffracted waves. Maystre et al. [11] theorized that the polarisation dependence arises when the ratio of wavelength to pitch ratio is greater than the order of 0.2.

Based on adequate knowledge of both theories, the decision to use the scalar theory was made as the blaze angle selection (showcased later) is below 5 degrees and scalar theory is a good approximation for calculation of efficiency parameters.

It is also good to note that the initial configuration of the GCM is to be tested with a coherent, collimated and monochromatic light source – an He-Ne laser of 632.8 nm . Hence, the Fraunhofer theory of diffraction or far field is a valid source of approximation.

3.1 MATLAB Simulation

We turn to MATLAB for extensive calculation and ease of use and availability. A Graphical User Interface is built for use as a calculator based on equations 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4. A snapshot of the GUI(Figure 3.4) built is showcased below.

Figure 3.4: Snapshot of the MATLAB GUI developed for calculation

This helps us calculate the blaze angle for each wavelength requirement. A compact table below (Table 3.1) highlights the achieved calculations.

Table 3.1: Blaze Angle Calculation

λ (μm)	d (μm)	Order	α (degrees)	β (degrees)	θ (degrees)	h (μm)
1.13	31.25	-1	18.9806101	-21.1867008	1.103045	0.6015807
1.47	31.25	-1	18.9806101	-21.8568031	1.438096	0.7842776
1.78	31.25	-1	18.9806101	-22.47052814	1.744959	0.9515803
1.92	31.25	-1	18.9806101	-22.74858309	1.883986	1.0273700

3.2 Czerny Turner Monochromator

Once the blaze angle calculations are understood in the previous section, we can look to start with the optics design of the Grating Characterization Monochromator (GCM) which is the primary focus of the thesis. The inspiration of design comes from two places : first, the Czerny Turner Monochromator and second, the Offner configuration of the SWIR payload itself.

The Czerny Turner Monochromator taken from the Diffraction Grating Handbook by C. Palmer consists of two concave mirrors and one planar grating. The primary mirror collimates the incoming light onto the grating (secondary mirror) and the tertiary mirror focuses the diffracted light onto a detector used. This configuration is chosen as the base optical design for the spectrometer characterisation setup. There are two problems to address once

Figure 3.5: Czerny Turner Monochromator.
Source : The Diffraction Grating Handbook

this scheme is understood. One is to translate this textbook design into a Zemax Lens File for a detailed analysis of major optical parameters. The second problem is to realise that the mirrors displayed in Figure 3.5 are spherical mirrors and a planar grating whereas the Offner of the payload uses has aspheric surface mirrors. With the spherical mirrors used in the Czerny-Turner, aberration correction is difficult to implement. Astigmatism and Coma

are prevalent in the case of spherical mirrors. The first model designed in Section 4.1.1 caters to the spherical mirror design more similar to the Czerny-Turner design. The second model in Section 4.1.2 shows the importance, design implications and aberration corrections while using aspheric surfaces.

3.3 Sine Bar Mechanism

The optical configuration once designed will have to be correlated such that the detector can be configured to be able to capture diffraction orders $(-2, -1, 0, +1, +2)$ for wavelengths ranging from 900 nm to 2500 nm . The Primary Mirror and Tertiary Mirrors are assumed to be fixed in their positions as any tilt or decenter can cause severe aberrations to the system. The grating however is in a suitable position to be rotated about its axis such that different orders can fall on the detector slit (exit slit).

This correlation can be made through a Sine Bar mechanism. This mechanism links the rotation of the grating such that each wavelength of -2 to $+2$ order will pass through the exit slit and is sensed by the detector placed behind the exit slit. The lever in Figure 3.6 is of a fixed length. Based on resolution requirements and coverage of wavelength from -2 to $+2$ orders, the length of the lever derived to be 272.22 mm . Thus, the grating can be maneuvered to collect multiple data points for each wavelength. Once the data can be collected via Comma Separated Value (.csv) file or a graphical plot, one can evaluate the Intensity Ratios and thus the Diffraction Efficiency of a grating which would fulfill the primary purpose of the Grating Characterisation Monochromator (GCM). Further data plotting for diffraction order against lead screw travel would currently require to import the .csv files into MATLAB and then plotting the results which is considered as a future scope of work.

$$\sin\phi = \frac{x}{L} \quad (3.5)$$

Where,

ϕ is the angle made between the grating and screw rod.

x is the linear travel distance on the screw rod.

L is the length of the lever which is moving the grating.

Figure 3.6: Sine Bar Mechanism Schematic

3.4 Diffraction Efficiency

As a grating is used, it is important to evaluate its efficiency. It must perform according to design. It is designed to increase the the intensity and amount of radiation or light in the -1^{st} order. The diffraction grating blaze wavelength are designed to have maximum efficiency where the transmission through the Earth’s atmospheric window is minimum. That is seen in Figure 2.1. Hence, the efficiency of the grating or the intensity distribution into the -1 order; is set to peak at the blaze wavelengths of 1130, 1470 and 1780 *nm*.

The Diffraction Grating Handbook [10] has defined a family of blaze angles for classification (Table 3.2). As per previous blaze angle calculations done in Table 3.1, it can be seen that the grating used for this study belongs to the family of very low blaze angles. With a very low blaze angle, polarisation effects can be ignored. This lets the use of scalar theory for predicting the diffraction efficiency of the grating used. Rigorous theory is primarily used to account for polarisation effects. There are two ways of defining and calculating

Table 3.2: Blaze Angle Classification

Family	Blaze Angle(θ_B) in degrees
very low	< 5
low	$5 < \theta_B < 10$
medium	$10 < \theta_B < 18$
special anomaly angle	$18 < \theta_B < 22$
high	$22 < \theta_B < 38$
very high	$\theta_B > 38$

Diffraction Efficiency (DE). Absolute efficiency is defined as the power of monochromatic light diffracted into the order being measured divided by the power of the incident light. While relative efficiency is defined as the power of monochromatic light diffracted into the order being measured divided by power of the specular reflection from a polished mirror coated with the same substrate under identical conditions. As per the Diffraction Grating Handbook, the absolute diffraction efficiency is approximately 50% at $0.7\lambda_B$ to $1.8\lambda_B$ where λ_B is the blaze wavelength.

The method used here however is a more direct approach. Once the calculation for the lead screw travel using the sine bar mechanism is validated experimentally, a highly accurate Spectroradiometer detector is used to acquire both the spectra (wavelength information) and the radiometric values (Digital Number or DN which gives the intensity information).

As the motor moves the grating gradually, the detector data is captured simultaneously. The GUI built controls both the grating rotation and the data acquired from the detector. As that information is exported, a MATLAB plot (which is done post data acquisition) gives a clear overview of the difference in intensities of the diffraction orders. The ratio of each order to another order or the zeroth order (which is total incident power) gives the diffraction efficiency of the grating to be evaluated. The resultant graphs are shown in Figures 5.7, 5.8 and 5.9.

Chapter 4

Grating Characterisation Monochromator

This chapter details the step by step iterative procedure followed to reach the final design of the Grating Characterisation Monochromator as a fully functional instrument. Zemax Optic Studio 22 and 23 has been used for all optical design analysis. The opto-mechanical and electronics assembly of the instrument was designed once the specifications post optical review was given. The assembly generated is showcased in later sections throughout the thesis report.

4.1 Zemax Simulation

4.1.1 First Conversion to Zemax

The first step taken is to define the aperture type. It is chosen to be Object Space Numerical Aperture. Also, as per requirements, a constant unit magnification is needed hence a checkbox for telecentric object space is selected. This instructs Zemax to assume that the entrance pupil is at infinity. For best performance, it is protocol to set the stop surface to surface 1 and it can be observed in the Lens Data Editor. The source is to be input through a slit and hence the fields in the field editor (used to define Field of View of the system) are not defined. The design is focused on keeping the aberrations and stray light to a minimum.

Figure 4.1 showcases the first design converted from the textbook and theoretical calculations to a Zemax Lens File. The ray trace is for is shown for an input slit configuration and output for a Focal Plane Array (FPA) detector. From an outwardly glance itself, it can be noticed that the rays are not focused. This can be due to aberrations like astigmatism,

Figure 4.1: Isometric View of Initial 3D Shaded Model.

coma, spherical aberration, defocus, distortion, curvature and many other assembly related reasons. The same system can be optimised by increasing the Optical Track Length ie. the distances between the mirrors and grating and Radius of Curvature (ROC) of the Mirrors. However, this would decrease the compactness. Also, this would deviate from the main purpose of the project of evaluating the customised grating for the SWIR payload. Before the next optimisation is made, the spherical mirrors are converted to aspherical mirrors. This brings the project closer to the goal of evaluating the grating efficiencies with the specific PM and TM of the SWIR Offner.

Figure 4.2 is the Lens Data Editor is where the author edits the system's ROC, distance between elements, clear aperture, change surface type and thermal coefficient of thermal expansion $s(CTE)$.

An attempt is made to explain each column's importance further. Surface type defines the kind of optical element (like a grating or mirror) we wish to include in the system, Zemax has a detailed list of each element and its parameters online for reference. The Comment column is for the user's purpose to enter their desired nomenclature; it doesn't affect the system. The Radius defines the Radius of Curvature of the corresponding sur-

	Surface Type	Comment	Radius	Thickness	Material	Semi-Diameter	Mech Semi-Dia	Conic	TCE x 1E-6
0	OBJECT	Standard ▾	Infinity	291.522		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
1	STOP	Coordinate Break ▾		0.000	-	0.000	-	-	-
2	(aper)	Standard ▾	Primary Mirror	-285.0...	MIRR...	90.000 U	-	0.000	0.000
3		Coordinate Break ▾		0.000	-	0.000	-	-	-
4		Coordinate Break ▾		0.000	-	0.000	-	-	-
5	(aper)	Standard ▾	Secondary Mirror	-143.2...	MIRR...	21.000 U	21.000	0.000	0.000
6		Coordinate Break ▾		134.997	-	0.000	-	-	-
7	(aper)	Standard ▾	Tertiary Mirror	-280.2...	MIRR...	100.000 U	-	0.000	0.000
8		Coordinate Break ▾		0.000	-	0.000	-	-	-
9	IMAGE (aper)	Standard ▾	Image plane	Infinity	-	16.000 U	-	0.000	0.000

Figure 4.2: Lens Data Editor of Initial Model

face. Thickness defines the distance to the next surface. Material lets the user define the kind of surface it is from a catalogue; like N-BK7 or ZnS Broad. Anti Reflection Coating can be defined in the coating column. For optical coating, a different software is generally preferred and then imported into Zemax. The Clear Semi-Diameter is the radial clear aperture required to pass all rays from all field points. Mechanical Semi-Diameter defines the surface radial dimension upto the mechanical edge of a lens. Conic defines the section of a cone to use as the base of an asphere. Furthermore, a diffraction grating has parameters like order and lines/ μm to define. The author makes use of the above parameters in building the GCM as explained in later sections.

4.1.2 First Iteration

The spherical surfaces are converted to aspheric surfaces to optimise the performance of the GCM further. The aspheric surfaces can be defined mathematically by the sag of the surface by Equation 4.1. When the aspheric terms ($A_i r^{2i}$) of Equation 4.1 are zero, the surface resulting from it is termed a conic.

$$z = \frac{cr^2}{1 + \sqrt{1 - (1 + k)c^2r^2}} + \sum_{n=1}^N A_i r^{2i}(x, y) \quad (4.1)$$

Where,

z is the surface sag parallel to the optical axis.
c is the base curvature at the vertex, inverse of radius.
r is the radial coordinate from the optical axis.
k is the conic constant type defined in Table 4.1. $k = -\epsilon^2$
 ϵ is the eccentricity.
 $A_i r^{2i}$ are higher order terms.

Table 4.1: Conic Section Types

Conic Constant (k)	Surface Type
$k < -1$	Hyperboloid
$k = -1$	Paraboloid
$-1 < k < 0$	Ellipsoid
$k = 0$	Sphere
$k > 0$	Oblate Ellipsoid

The next step is to define groove density ie. lines/ μm . The groove density of the grating is 32 lines/mm so the input in Zemax is 0.032. The order selected for covering 900 to 2500nm of SWIR wavelengths is -1 order. However, in the building of the GCM the goal is to scan 900 to 2500 nm wavelengths of orders from -2 to +2 (ie. -2, -1, 0, +1, +2). The author explains this mechanism and method in the coming sections.

There are two ways to look to implement an aspheric surface in Zemax. One by keep the corresponding rows in the Conic column as a variable and optimise in the Merit Function Editor. Another way is to use the option of 'Find Best Asphere' in the Optimise tab and then choose the number of terms you wish you Zemax to sort through. The author optimises for obtaining the best Modulation Transfer Function (MTF) at 17 line pairs per mm ($\frac{lp}{mm}$). This comes from the Nyquist rate given in Equation 4.2.

$$SpatialFrequency(lp/mm) = \frac{1000}{2f_s} = \frac{1000}{2 * pixelpitch} = \frac{1000}{2 * 30} = 16.6 \quad (4.2)$$

The next set of optimisation is done for getting a good spot diagram and as close to a diffraction limited performance Airy Disc as possible.

$$r = 1.22 * \lambda * f / \# \quad (4.3)$$

Where,

r is the radius of the Airy Disc or radius to the first zero.

λ is the wavelength of length

f/# is the f number.

Surface #	Surface Type	Comment	Radius	Thickness	Material	Semi-Diameter	Conic	TCE x 1E-6	Decenter X	Decenter Y
0	OBJECT	Standard	Infinity	291.522		0.000	0.000	0.000		
1	STOP	Coordinate Break		0.000	-	0.000		-	0.000	-47.000
2	(aper)	Standard	Primary mirror -285.023	-140.003	MIRROR	90.000 U	-8.160E-03	0.000		
3		Coordinate Break		0.000	-	0.000		-	0.000	0.188
4		Coordinate Break		0.000	-	0.000		-	0.000	0.000
5	(aper)	Diffraction Grating	Grating -143.272	0.000	MIRROR	21.000 U	-0.038	0.000	0.032	-1.000
6		Coordinate Break		134.997	-	0.000		-	0.000	0.000
7	(aper)	Standard	Tertiary mirror -280.225	-277.439 V	MIRROR	100.000 U	-9.922E-03	0.000		
8		Coordinate Break		0.000	-	0.000		-	0.000	-55.137
9	IMAGE (aper)	Standard	Image plane	Infinity		16.000 U	0.000	0.000		

Figure 4.3: Lens Data Editor of 2nd model

Once this optimisation is done, the author goes back to the LDE and notices that Zemax has replaced the initial values for aspheres to best fit our demands. Figure 4.3 shows the LDE values after optimisation. As per Table 4.1, the Primary and Tertiary Mirror surfaces are termed as Concave Oblate Ellipsoids while the Grating is a Convex Oblate Ellipsoid.

4.1.3 Second Iteration

Once we have achieved a near optimum configuration, we look to optimise further by replacing the surface type with Even or Odd Aspheres which consist of higher order coefficient terms from Equation 4.1. This lets us simulate and realise Equation 4.1. Aspherics let us correct for aberrations while maintaining the compactness of the system.

For the second iteration, an Even Asphere is used for surface 2 and surface 7, or Primary and Tertiary Mirror. This was done in an effort to maximise the system performance. The parameters taken into consideration are as follows :

- **Spot Diagram** : The rays traced are within Airy Disc or close so that the system's performance can be considered to be diffraction limited.

	Surface Type	Comment	Radius	Thickness	Material	Semi-Diameter	Conic	TCE x 1E-6	2nd Order Ter	4th Order Term	6th Order Term
0	OBJECT	Standard	Infinity	291.522		0.000	0.000	0.000			
1	STOP	Coordinate Break		0.000	-	0.000		-	0.000	-47.000	0.000
2	(aper)	Even Asphere	Primary Mirr...	-285.0...	-140.003	MIRROR	90.000 U	-0.014 V	0.000	-2.498E-11 V	0.000
3		Coordinate Break		0.000	-	0.000		-	0.000	0.188	0.000
4		Coordinate Break		0.000	-	0.000		-	0.000	0.000	0.000
5	(aper)	Diffraction Grating	Grating	-143.2...	0.000	MIRROR	21.000 U	-0.042 V	0.000	0.032	-1.000
6		Coordinate Break		134.997	-	0.000		-	0.000	0.000	0.000 P
7	(aper)	Even Asphere	Tertiary Mirror	-280.2...	-277.379	MIRROR	100.000 U	-0.015 V	0.000	-5.159E-11 V	0.000
8		Coordinate Break		0.000	-	0.000		-	0.000	-55.137	0.000
9	IMAGE (aper)	Standard	Image plane	Infinity	-	16.000 U	0.000	0.000			

Figure 4.4: Lens Data Editor of 3rd model

- **FFT MTF** : MTF is calculated using Fraunhofer Diffraction Theory and FFT Algorithm. As calculated from 4.2, the system MTF is to be evaluated at 17 lp/mm.
- **Diffraction Enclosed Energy** : The encircled energy is to be evaluated at either around airy disc radius or RMS radius or detector pitch. The energy density curve generated tells the energy enclosed within a certain distance from centroid.
- **Wavefront Map** : The wavefront error in RMS units is to be evaluated as well.

Note : While optimising, it must be taken care that the values of focal length, f number and optical track length must not change much. Hence, we enter the targeted values of 2682.17mm for EEFL, 3.81 for WFNO and 282.44mm for TOTR in merit function editor before optimising.

4.2 Comparison of Key Performance Parameters

Spot Diagram :

Figure 4.5: Spot Diagram of 2nd model

Figure 4.6: Spot Diagram of 3rd model

The Airy Disc is easy to distinguish by the black circle around the predicted ray trace simulated in Zemax. There are two terms that are also enclosed within the figures 4.5 and 4.6. They are namely; RMS and Geo Radius. RMS is a better quantity to refer to as it provides a better sampling of spot generated from corresponding field points while Geo radius gives points furthest away. The reference is to the Chief Ray throughout analysis. As per the Figures 4.5 and 4.6, it can be seen that Airy Disc diameter, RMS spot size, Geo radius is smaller in third model and thus from the Spot Size point of view, third model is preferred.

The 1st model is not considered for a comparison analysis because it uses spherical mirrors and there was ample scope of improvement by using conic mirrors in place of spherical mirrors and aspheric mirrors as simulated in model two and three respectively. As per observation, it can be seen that the 2nd model constructed provides a spot diagram with a larger airy radius than the 3rd. The 3rd model shows that the RMS spot remains within the airy throughout multiple wavelength configurations except for the Geo radius being larger for the first configuration of 0.9 μm . Thus, model 3 is preferred.

FFT MTF :

However, further analysis of aberrations and MTF is also required.

$$OTF = |OTF|e^{iPTF} = MTFe^{iPTF} \quad (4.4)$$

Where,

OTF is the Optical Transfer Function.

MTF is the Modulation Transfer Function.

PTF is the Phase Transfer Function.

The Optical Transfer Function (OTF) describes an optical system's response as a function of spatial frequencies. The Modulation Transfer Function (MTF) is the modulus of the OTF and the Phase Transfer Function (PTF) is the complex valued term contributing to the OTF description. MTF uses two quantities to objectively quantify image quality : resolution and contrast. Resolution is the ability to distinguish object details and is expressed in line pairs per mm ($\frac{lp}{mm}$). Contrast or modulation is the ability to make apart the intensity difference. Another way to define contrast of a system is how well the maximum and minimum intensity values are seen and translated from object plane and then onto the image plane.

Figure 4.7: MTF Analysis of 2nd model

Figure 4.8: MTF Analysis of 3rd model

The diffraction-limited performance curve is the linear curve colour coded black at the topmost of each graph for figures 4.7 and 4.8. Upon further analysis of the system at a spatial frequency of $17 \left(\frac{lp}{mm}\right)$ (refer to equation 4.2), it is noted that the 3rd model (Figure 4.8 follows a curve quite close to the ideal diffraction-limited curve. Thus, model three is preferred. As per standards, it has been made sure that the evaluation is done at multiple wavelengths. Hence, the Multi Configuration Editor is made use of again and cycled through for different wavelengths and the FFT MTF is recorded.

Diffraction Encircled Energy :

Once the MTF performance is evaluated, we move onto the next important parameter that is the Encircled Energy. Encircled Energy is to be defined as the amount of radiometric power gathered within a circle on the target as a function of the radius of that target area. For an imaging system, encircled energy is the measure of the energy density of a focused spot. Consider a scenario where we have a point source or close to point source object. Aberrations in the system will affect the spot generated and create a Point Spread Function (PSF); a perfect system creates an airy disc (refer to equation 4.3). Before evaluating the performance of the models in terms of diffraction encircled energy, the author wanted to show the difference in Airy Disc image formed (refer to 4.9 2nd model and 4.10 for 3rd model.)

As can be referred from Figures 4.11 and 4.12, the change in performance can be noted for both models. The difference is evident between the two while evaluating in the first configuration of $0.9 \mu\text{m}$. However, both models have a very good percentage (>85%) of their energy enclosed within the detector pixel whose size is $30 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 4.9: Airy Disc Image 2nd model

Figure 4.10: Airy Disc Image of 3rd model

Note : Both models are f/3.8 and shown in the third configuration whose wavelength is 1.7 μm .

Figure 4.11: Encircled Energy of 2nd model

Figure 4.12: Encircled Energy of 3rd model

Figure 4.13: Wavefront Map of 2nd model

Figure 4.14: Wavefront Map of 3rd model

Wavefront Map :

The next parameter looked into was the Wavefront Error Map which would show the deviation of the actual wavefront from an ideal reference wavefront. The deviation from an ideal reference wavefront was lesser for the 3rd model. The RMS wavefront error values

of model three are lesser than that of model 2 and hence model three is the preferred choice.

There are several other parameters in Zemax that allows us to perform a detailed comparative analysis. For the comparison analysis in this thesis report however, the author is constrained to the above mentioned parameters that give us a clear idea of the system performance throughout.

The comparison review report has brought to light how higher order aspheres once optimised well and used in a design outperform not just spherical mirrors but also conic aspherics on the basis of discussed parameters.

Since, all the Offner mirrors such as Primary Mirror (PM), the grating (SM) and the tertiary Mirror (TM) are made out of space grade Aluminum and manufactured using SPDT machining processes at PDSTL, the mirrors with higher order coefficients were realised. Thus, the 3rd model is chosen and given for fabrication and testing. Figure 4.15 show-cases the chosen model with all configurations enabled. The wavelength dispersion by the grating at the image plane is seen clearly.

Figure 4.15: 3–D layout with ray trace of chosen model with all configurations enabled

4.3 Zemax Iteration Review

A comparison analysis was done to show the differences between the 2nd and 3rd model. The comparison analysis shown in Section 4.2 is based on the above critical parameters.

There are five multi-configuration modes made to simulate the critical SWIR wavelengths. Each configuration corresponds to a given critical wavelength. The first configuration is for 0.9 μm , second for 1.4 μm , third for 1.7 μm , fourth for 2.3 μm and fifth for 2.5 μm . These configurations are made in the Multi Configuration Editor shown in Figure 4.16. An additional configuration is made later for calibration in front of laser source of 633 nm .

Figure 4.16: Multi Configuration Editor

4.4 Sine Bar Mechanism Calculation

The process for obtaining the angles for the Sine Bar mechanism mentioned in section 3.3 is described here. The process requires using the Merit Function Editor and knowledge of the operands to be used. Two operands are of interest : *REAY* and *RAID*. *REAY* gives the

real ray y-coordinate in lens units (*mm* in this case) at the surface required. This gives the location of different wavelengths at the image plane as per their chosen order. *RAID* gives the real ray angle of incidence defined as the angle in degrees between the surface normal and the incident ray at the surface required. For visualising the locations of the ray trace for each diffraction order at the image plane, please refer to Appendix A.3. The table used to calculate and calibrate with a Helium-Neon (He-Ne) laser of 632.8 *nm* is shown in table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Sine Bar Mechanism Calculation

Diffraction Order	λ (<i>nm</i>)	y distance from detector	ϕ wrt 0 order	x distance
-2	900	-0.465	-1.76927	-8.375
-2	633	2.029	-1.27769	-6.07
-1	900	3.723	-0.88147	-4.187
-1	633	4.970	-0.63986	-3.04
0	all	7.91	0	0
+1	633	10.089	0.63986	3.04
+1	900	12.095	0.88144	1.185
+2	633	13.788	1.27980	6.08
+2	900	16.28	1.76349	8.37

Note : The length of the lever is 272.22 *mm*. All calculations have been carried out thus.

In table 4.2, λ is the wavelength in *nm*, the third column is the distance or coordinate of the chosen order and wavelength's ray trace which is falling on the image plane. The design implementation as said before is configured such that -1 order of the central wavelength of 1700 *nm* falls on the detector center and I show that detail in A.4. The y coordinate data is acquired by using the *REAY* operand in the The Merit Function Editor in Zemax. By changing the orders and configurations, The fourth column is the angle of rotation of grating that needs to be implemented by using the lever in the sine bar mechanism where ϕ is the angle in degrees. The fifth column is the linear distance of travel on the screw rod.

4.5 Tolerancing

The step before giving optical components for manufacture, a critical process called tolerancing is done in Zemax. Tolerancing can be defined as accounting for manufacturing error and seeing to it that whether the built system meets its intended purpose.

In the Tolerancing Editor located in the Tolerancing tab, high precision tolerances are applied for all GCM design parameters. There are several standards of performance of tolerancing and the author has used the standard allocated by Zemax. A sample Tolerance editor for the precision tolerance performed is shown in Figure 4.17. The tolerance report generated is set to store the best and worst configurations and the Tolerance data summary gives the information regarding worst offenders. It also tells us the amount of tilt or decenter error that can arise during optical alignment that would impact the system. It can be seen (figure 4.17) that tolerancing for the central wavelength of SWIR ie. $1.7 \mu\text{m}$ and also for all other configurations (refer to figure 4.16 meaning 0.9, 1.4, 1.7, 2.4 and $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ wavelengths. From the File tab of Zemax, the CAD model is exported and submitted for review and fabrication. A summary report is attached in Appendix A.5.

The screenshot displays the 'Tolerance Presets' dialog box in Zemax. It is configured for a 'Generic' vendor and 'Precision' grade. The 'Surface Tolerances' section includes:

- Radius: 0.02 Millimeters
- Thickness: 0.05 Millimeters
- Decenter X: 0.025 Millimeters
- Decenter Y: 0.025 Millimeters
- Tilt X: 0.0333 Degrees
- Tilt Y: 0.0333 Degrees
- S + A Irregularity: 1 Fringes (unchecked)
- Zernike Irregularity: 0.2 Fringes (checked)

 The 'Element Tolerances' section includes:

- Decenter X: 0.02
- Decenter Y: 0.02
- Tilt X: 0.02 Degrees
- Tilt Y: 0.02 Degrees

 The 'Index Tolerances' section includes:

- Index: 0.0005
- Abbe %: 0.7

 The 'Options' section includes:

- Start At Row: 1
- Test Wavelength: 1.7
- Start At Surface: 1
- Stop At Surface: 9 - image plane
- Use Focus Compensation: checked

Figure 4.17: Precision Tolerance Sample Presets

4.6 Stray Light Analysis

For any optical system, a complete and thorough stray light analysis must be done to account for any incoming unwanted strays and/or ghost reflections. The author has attempted to carry out a sequential analysis. Detailed non-sequential analysis is to be carried out as a future scope of the project. Non-Sequential Stray Analysis can be done in TracePro and FRED. However, since Zemax supports sequential and non-sequential workflow, two features are explored initially in sequential mode : Ghost Focus Generator and YNI Contributions. Before the author shows the results obtained, the difference in sequential and non-sequential workflow is explained. Sequential workflow is used for design, optimisation and tolerancing. Whereas, Non-Sequential is generally recommended for illumination analysis, stray light. Non-Sequential analysis takes optical analysis a step further by randomising the ray trace and making sure that the ray trace doesn't happen in a chronological order unlike Sequential wherein the system makes sure the rays passed by a user defined serial path.

Ghost Focus Generator helps in the analysis and detection of ghost reflections occurring in the system. There are certain instances when the use of larger mirrors or lenses cause back reflections to occur such that there's a double bounce of two surfaces and then unwanted rays reach the image plane. This makes it difficult for detection. The results obtained indicate there being marginal rays traversing through the GCM system and reaching the image plane thereby hampering image quality. For the detailed results, please refer to Appendix A.1.

The YNI Contributions is for looking at the Narcissus value. Narcissus [12] is a phenomenon in Infrared Imaging when the detector is sensing background radiation via reflections off of surfaces and affects imaging. More importance in this report is given to the Ghost Focus Generator. For the detailed results of YNI Contributions, please refer to Appendix A.2.

Owing to the stray analysis report generated, a suggestion was made to include a baffle behind the grating and between the source and detector slit. Also, there are black anodised lateral vanes along the sides of the GCM to cut off stray light.

4.7 Mechanical and Electronic Assembly

As the optical configuration is chosen and given for fabrication, the mechanical and electronics have to also be made in tandem. Mechanical components have to be black anodised and vanes to be installed on the sides for stray light blocking. The mechanical housing was designed in NX Siemens by PDSTL while the electronics interfacing was supported by Shri Kulasekaran M of IIT Bombay. The Graphical User Interface (GUI) developed for the interfacing the GCM components with the detector and grating rotation was done in LabVIEW. The mechanical housing along with the associated electronics mounted in shown in figure 4.18. Figure 4.19 shows the CAD model views of the critical Sine Bar Mechanism designed including the travel along the screw rod as the stepper motor drives it.

Figure 4.18: Mechanical Assembly of GCM

Figure 4.19: CAD views of Sine Bar Mechanism. (a) Side View of Sine bar lever. (b) Side view portraying the linear travel of x for moving the grating. (c) Bottom view showing the screw rod

Chapter 5

Experimental Results

As the optical, mechanical and electronic components are manufactured, the next step is to assemble the Grating Characterisation Monochromator. The higher order even aspheric mirrors fabricated are made of space-grade aluminium (Al-6061). The surfaces of the Primary and Tertiary mirrors are termed as Concave Oblate Ellipsoids and the grating as Convex Oblate Ellipsoid. They are coated with high efficiency reflective coatings. The grooves on the convex surface mirror are vertical so the diffraction spreads on the detector plane horizontally (perpendicular to the slit orientation). The input source and detector slit are each of $90\ \mu\text{m}$. The initial results are carried out in front of a He-Ne laser of $632.8\ \text{nm}$. Further experiments aim to utilise a broadband source called a Quartz Tungsten Halogen (QTH) lamp for obtaining the entire spectrum including visible and Short Wavelength IR as a future scope of work.

5.1 Spectroradiometer SR-4500

The detector used for carryout experiments is a highly accurate and compact spectroradiometer provided by Instruments Research and Development Establishment (IRDE-DRDO), Dehradun. It has been previously used for several field experiments including on-site radiometric calibration of satellite systems. The SR-4500 Spectroradiometer is UV/VIS/NIR manufactured and supplied by Spectral Evolution based in USA. Its features are :

- Spectral range of 350-2500nm
- 512 element TE-cooled silicon photodiode array (350-1000 nm) with spectral resolution of 3 nm and sampling bandwidth of 1.5 nm .

- 256 element TE-cooled extended InGaAs photodiode array (1000-1900 nm) with spectral resolution of 8 nm and sampling bandwidth of 3.8 nm .
- 256 element TE-cooled extended InGaAs photodiode array (1900-2500 nm) with spectral resolution of 6 nm and sampling bandwidth of 2.5 nm .
- Diffraction-based optics for greater reliability (no moving parts)
- DARWin SP Data Acquisition Software for ease of access to data recording.

Figure 5.1: The Spectroradiometer SR-4500 used as detector

5.2 Optical Alignment and Metrology

Assembly of an optical setup is a crucial task. Generally for precision grade optics, a Fizeau interferometer based setup alongside a Theodolite is used. The *ZygoTM* interferometer is a

Fizeau interferometer of common path for the object and reference waves; it is the industry standard for non contact measurement of surface shape and transmitted wavefront. The mirrors and grating are first bonded to their mounts and then fixed onto the predetermined positions. The placement accuracy of the optical components and their mounts is judged by the Zygo interferometer and theodolite. The interferometric alignment was carried out by experts in the field headed by Shri Somashekar S and Shri Krishnamurthy T. The author is grateful to have been part of this critical process.

Figure 5.2: Zygo interferometer and Leica Theodolite used to assemble the GCM

5.3 Apparatus Assembled

As an image is worth a thousand words, the author would like to portray a few images to show the final achieved system of the Grating Characterisation Monochromator (GCM) and also enable the reader to be able to correctly visualise before showcasing the experimental results.

Figure 5.3: Labelled Diagram showcasing the GCM components interfaced

Figure 5.4: Labelled Diagram showcasing the Sine Bar Mechanism in practice

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.5: (a) GCM illuminated with a QTH Source. (b) Author holding a white paper to show the visible spectra split by the grating

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.6: (a) The author watching the GCM in operation. (b) Left to Right : Shri Krishnamurthy T, Shri Kulakekaran M, Shri Vinay, Shri Shashi.

5.4 Calibration and Validation

As the GCM is assembled and ready for experimentation, the first step is to calibrate the sine bar mechanism. For that, two calibration blocks are placed along either side of the micrometer screw rod each of 56.75 mm . The stepper motor requires a homing sequence each time it is operated to make the sure the zero order of all wavelengths of the grating is exactly at the center of the screw rod ie. when the lever is perfectly perpendicular to the screw rod. By movement of the lever, on either side of the center position of screw rod one can obtain the desired spectrum of $-2, -1, 0, +1, +2$ orders. The next step is to perform a first time calculation to check whether the theoretically calculated values in Table 4.2 are matching the experimental results desired.

After performing a few runs, it was discovered that there was an offset in the experimental values of the linear distance of travel along the screw rod (x) from the theoretically calculated values. Table 5.1 is to highlight that offset. It is noted that there is an offset of 0.89 mm . Knowing the calibration factor, the data is acquired.

Table 5.1: Sine Bar Mechanism Theoretical vs Experimental Values

Diffraction Order	$\lambda(nm)$	Theoretical travel	Experimental travel
-2	633	-6.07	-6.96
-1	633	-3.04	-3.93
0	all	0	-0.89
+1	633	3.04	2.15
+2	633	6.08	5.19

5.5 Diffraction Efficiency Results

The detector data is acquired and stored in a *.csv format opening in MS Excel. As the Excel data in input into the MATLAB program written by the author, the energy distribution is quite evident. The grating can now be validated as working per design and meeting its requirements. The readings taken here are of a He-Ne laser of 632.8 nm wavelength. The intensity ratios and diffraction efficiency are evaluated and shown in Table 5.2. The MATLAB plots show (Figure 5.7 and Figure 5.8) the demarcation and difference in orders as well. The author has also prepared a plot(Figure 5.9)to show the linear travel distance on the screw rod versus the intensity distribution/variation across the diffraction orders for

a laser source. With this tabular and graphical result, it marks the success of the Grating Characterisation Monochromator (GCM) which was built for the explicit purpose of carrying out diffraction efficiency measurements and further evaluate for other wavelengths using QTH Source and Spectral Line Filters. Please note that the tabular data (Table 5.2

Figure 5.7: (a) +1 order intensity. (b) -1 order intensity

Figure 5.8: (a) +2 order intensity. (b) -2 order intensity

corresponds to the set of readings shown in Figure 5.9. Figures 5.7 and 5.8 correspond to a second set of readings taken for 632.8 nm. As per the absolute diffraction efficiency of a blazed grating definition, the evaluated grating's peak efficiency will be enhanced at the blaze wavelength with a bandwidth of $0.7\lambda_B$ to $1.8\lambda_B$ where λ_B . Since, 632.8 nm is out

Figure 5.9: Distribution of Diffraction Orders versus Linear travel distance on screw rod.

Table 5.2: Intensity Ratio Results

$\lambda(nm)$	Order	DN/Intensity	Order ratio	Intensity Ratio
633	-1	1350	Reference	Reference
633	+1	370	-1 to +1	3.6486
633	-2	240	-1 to -2	5.625
633	+2	115	-1 to +2	11.739

of the blaze wavelength bandwidth absolute efficiency could not be evaluated. However, the relative efficiency is evaluated using the intensity ratios of -1 order 632.8 nm to other orders of 632.8nm (refer to (Table 5.2)). From the table it is noted that blazing the grating in -1 order has greatly enhanced the efficiency of the grating. Similar intensity ratios of other wavelengths of -1 order need to be evaluated using a broadband source like a Quartz Tungsten Halogen (QTH) Lamp containing SWIR wavelengths. Thus, the GCM built as the primary scope of this project greatly helps in evaluating different gratings of the SWIR Offner, blazed at different wavelengths with different groove densities.

5.6 Future Work

Despite its initial success, the GCM does have its limitations. Since it was built to cater to a specific payload's (SWIR Hyperspectral Imager) grating requirements, the optical setup cannot be generalised for other convex gratings of different ROC and higher order aspheric coefficients. Suitable Auxiliary Optics (AO) may be tried to improve the system so it can be used for a few other set of different gratings subject to the Offner optics focuses the entrance slit onto the exit slit with unit magnification.

Bibliography

- [1] A. Offner, “Unit power imaging catoptric anastigmat,” Jul. 24 1973, uS Patent 3,748,015.
- [2] M. P. Chrisp, “Convex diffraction grating imaging spectrometer,” Mar. 9 1999, uS Patent 5,880,834.
- [3] H. Li, X. Peng, C. Guan, and H. Hu, “Progress in the preparation and characterization of convex blazed gratings for hyper-spectral imaging spectrometer: A review,” *Micromachines*, vol. 13, no. 10, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-666X/13/10/1689>
- [4] J. Reimers, A. Bauer, K. Thompson, and J. Rolland, “Freeform spectrometer enabling increased compactness,” *Light Sci Appl.*, 2017.
- [5] V. Moreau, B. Borguet, J.-F. Jamoye, L. Maresi, A. Z. Marchi, and M. Miranda, “Freeform grating-based hyperspectral instruments: When smallsat solutions benefit to big missions,” 2019.
- [6] E. G. Loewen, E. K. Popov, L. V. Tsonev, and J. Hoose, “Experimental study of local and integral efficiency behavior of a concave holographic diffraction grating,” *Journal of the Optical Society of America A*, vol. 7, 1990.
- [7] P. Mouroulis, D. W Wilson, P. D Maker, and R. E Muller, “Convex grating types for concentric imaging spectrometers,” *Optica*, vol. 37, 1998.
- [8] M. A. Davies, B. S. Dutterer, T. J. Suleski, J. F. Silny, and E. D. Kim, “Diamond machining of diffraction gratings for imaging spectrometers,” *Precision Engineering*, vol. 36, no. 10, 2012. [Online]. Available: (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0141635911001401>)

- [9] M. Hettrick and S. Bowyer, "Variable line-space gratings: new designs for use in grazing incidence spectrometers," *Applied optics*, vol. 22, pp. 3921–4, 12 1983.
- [10] C. Palmer, "Diffraction grating handbook. mks instruments," *Inc.: New York, NY, USA*, 2020.
- [11] D. Maystre, "I rigorous vector theories of diffraction gratings," in *Progress in optics*. Elsevier, 1984, vol. 21, pp. 1–67. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0079663808701215>
- [12] J. W. Howard and I. R. Abel, "Narcissus: reflections on retroreflections in thermal imaging systems," *Applied Optics*, vol. 21, no. 18, pp. 3393–3397, 1982.

Appendix A

Appendix A Zemax Data

A.1 Ghost Focus Generator Data

This section shows the data generated in Zemax using the Sequential Stray Light Analysis feature of Ghost Focus Generator. It enabled the visualisation of the number of ghost or back reflections occurring in the system.

Surface 2 is the Primary Mirror

Surface 5 is the Grating

Surface 7 is the Tertiary Mirror

Surface 9 is the Image Plane

Units are Millimeters.

Wavelength: 1.700000 μm Type: Double Bounces The '*****' denotes a possible internal focus RMS is the RMS spot radius on axis at the primary wavelength. RMS values of 0.00 indicate that an accurate RMS could not be computed, usually due to ray errors.

Ghost reflection off surface 5 then 2. (GH005002.zmx)

Surf	Marginal	F/#	RMS
3	-1.2526E+00	3.773701	8.7312E-01
Marginal ray height :	-1.2526		
Chief ray height :	0.0000		
Distance to ghost pupil:	-1581.3123		
Distance to ghost focus:	9.4538		
Effective focal length :	4119.9258		

Ghost reflection off surface 7 then 5. (GH007005.zmx)

Surf	Marginal	F/#	RMS
9	-7.2207E-01	3.845825	1.2026E+00
Marginal ray height :	-0.7221		
Chief ray height :	0.0000		
Distance to ghost pupil:	-130.7133		
Distance to ghost focus:	5.5539		
Effective focal length :	-156.1368		

Ghost reflection off surface 7 then 2. (GH007002.zmx)

Surf	Marginal	F/#	RMS
3	-7.2207E-01	3.845825	1.2026E+00
Marginal ray height :	-0.7221		
Chief ray height :	0.0000		
Distance to ghost pupil:	-130.7133		
Distance to ghost focus:	5.5539		
Effective focal length :	-156.1368		

Ghost reflection off surface 9 then 7. (GH009007.zmx)

Surf	Marginal	F/#	RMS
13	-8.2548E-03	3.778121	1.1993E-02
Marginal ray height :	-0.0083		
Chief ray height :	0.0000		
Distance to ghost pupil:	-1507.8599		
Distance to ghost focus:	-0.0624		
Effective focal length :	-1341.1728		

Ghost reflection off surface 9 then 5. (GH009005.zmx)

Surf	Marginal	F/#	RMS
9	-8.2548E-03	3.778121	1.1993E-02
Marginal ray height :	-0.0083		
Chief ray height :	0.0000		
Distance to ghost pupil:	-1507.8599		
Distance to ghost focus:	-0.0624		
Effective focal length :	-1341.1728		

Ghost reflection off surface 9 then 2. (GH009002.zmx)

Surf	Marginal	F/#	RMS
3	-8.2548E-03	3.778121	1.1993E-02
Marginal ray height :	-0.0083		
Chief ray height :	0.0000		
Distance to ghost pupil:	-1507.8599		
Distance to ghost focus:	-0.0624		
Effective focal length :	-1341.1728		

Closest ghost pupil : -130.7133 at 7 then 5
 Closest ghost focus : -0.0624 at 9 then 7

A.2 YNI Contributions

This lists the paraxial YNI value which is proportional to the Narcissus contribution of that surface.

Listing of YNI contributions

Date : 28-04-2023
Configuration 3 of 5

Units are Millimeters.
Wavelength: 1.70000 μm

Surf	YNI
1	5.10599
2	-0.11643
3	-2.65795
4	-2.65795
5	-0.08289
6	2.49218
7	-0.04778
8	-0.00055

A.3 Diffraction Order Locations

The spread and location for all required orders of all configurations is shown below.

Figure A.1: -2 order

Figure A.2: -1 order

Figure A.3: 0 order

Figure A.4: +1 order

Figure A.5: +2 order

A.4 Sine Bar Mechanism Calculation

Following is the detailed calculation table of the ingenious sine bar mechanism using which the GCM is to be operated for scanning.

Note : The length of the lever is 272.22 mm. All calculations have been carried out thus.

Diffraction Order	Wavelength (nm)	Y-distance from detector center	Phi wrt zeroth order (angle of rotation of grating)	x-distance wrt. the zeroth order
2	2500	31.152	4.906045029	23.242
2	1700	23.717	3.333096842	15.807
2	900	16.28	1.763495687	8.37
2	632	13.788	1.279800561	6.08
1	2500	19.534	2.449875429	11.624
1	1700	15.815	1.665453826	7.905
1	900	12.095	0.881446061	4.185
1	632	10.089	0.6398603713	3.04
0	all lambda	7.91	0	0
-1	632	4.970	-0.6398603713	-3.04
-1	900	3.723	-0.881472997	-4.187
-1	1700	0	-1.665099613	-7.91
-1	2500	-3.724	-2.448936725	-11.634
-2	632	-2.029	-1.277695277	-6.07
-2	900	-0.465	-1.762971006	-8.375
-2	1700	-7.915	-3.331252051	-15.825
-2	2500	-15.372	-4.902258816	-23.282

A.5 Tolerance Data Details

The following two tables contain the summary of the tolerance reports generated. This indicates the amount of change that can occur from manufacturing and the effects on the performance of the system. The worst offenders are the changes that hamper the system performance the most. The first column tell the type of change that is indicated in the row while the second and third columns tell the surface number. The fourth column tells the amount of change in *mm*. In the first column, TETX is Tilt in X, TETY is tilt in Y, TEDY is decenter in Y.

Worst offenders:			Value	Criterion	Change
Type					
TETX	7	7	0.20000000	0.05626828	0.05012967
TETX	2	2	-0.20000000	0.05326445	0.04712584
TETX	7	7	-0.20000000	0.05173632	0.04559771
TETX	2	2	0.20000000	0.04428636	0.03814775
TETY	7	7	-0.20000000	0.03963652	0.03349791
TETY	7	7	0.20000000	0.03963652	0.03349791
TETY	2	2	-0.20000000	0.03229474	0.02615613
TETY	2	2	0.20000000	0.03229474	0.02615613
TEDY	7	7	0.20000000	0.01502762	0.00888901
TEDY	2	2	-0.20000000	0.01394945	0.00781084

Worst offenders:

Type			Value	Criterion	Change
TETX	7	7	-0.20000000	0.04895722	0.04814459
TETX	2	2	-0.20000000	0.04744001	0.04662737
TETX	7	7	0.20000000	0.04653541	0.04572278
TETX	2	2	0.20000000	0.04561153	0.04479890
TETY	7	7	-0.20000000	0.03448250	0.03366987
TETY	7	7	0.20000000	0.03448250	0.03366987
TETY	2	2	0.20000000	0.03131360	0.03050096
TETY	2	2	-0.20000000	0.03131360	0.03050096
TEDY	7	7	-0.20000000	0.01047807	0.00966543
TEDY	2	2	0.20000000	0.00996007	0.00914744

